

THREE-DIMENSIONAL MODELING AND EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF DAMAGE ACCUMULATION IN OPEN HOLE COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Development of a high fidelity strength prediction tool for laminated composites with stress concentrations is an important problem for the aerospace industry as well as less traditional areas of composite applications, such as rail-transportation and sports equipment industries. High fidelity modeling involves simulation of actual damage mechanisms such as matrix cracking, delaminations and their combined influence on the redistribution of fiber stresses, which determines the strength. Discrete modeling of transverse cracking represents a formidable problem. Normally the mesh configuration is dictated by the boundaries of the specimen, such as the presence of a hole. Transverse cracking directions in the plies are defined by fiber orientations and change from ply to ply. Higher order shape functions will be employed below to construct an efficient method for mesh independent discontinuity modeling. The surface of the displacement jump associated with transverse cracking is defined in terms of the domain Heaviside function approximated by using higher order polynomial B-splines. It is shown that the approximation of the Heaviside function maintains the integral properties of the step function and that the gradient of the approximation maintains the integral properties of Dirac's delta function for any order of approximation. An advantage of the proposed method is that its implementation only involves integration of the products of original shape functions and their derivatives and does not require modification of the integration domains. Experimental verification included detailed damage propagation characterization by using incremental loading x-ray technique and full-field strain measurement based on the moiré interferometry technique.

KEY WORDS: Open hole, composite, splitting, B-spline, mesh independent crack modeling

INTRODUCTION

To provide accurate strength prediction in notched composites, it is important to take into account the stress redistribution due to damage progression prior to failure. Both two- and three-dimensional models have been developed for strength prediction of composites with open and filled holes. In the present paper we shall focus mostly on three-dimensional models, where each ply is explicitly modeled as initially orthotropic material. Our interest in three-dimensional models transpires from the fact that only within this framework phenomena such as stacking sequence effect [1] as well as influence of the through the thickness loading effects, such as clamp-up on strength, can be addressed rigorously.

Three-dimensional property-degradation based progressive damage finite element analysis in open hole composite laminates was first performed about twenty years ago [2]. A quasi-isotropic [0/45/-45/90]_s polymer composite laminate was analyzed. Three damage modes were considered (i) fiber failure, (ii) transverse failure or intraply cracking and (iii) delamination. In each case both the respective normal and shear stress components were checked in the center of each element to determine local failure. When the failure was detected in a particular element its elastic properties were modified (degraded) in

the following manner for each damage mode: (i)- all components of the stiffness matrix were made equal to zero, (ii) all components of the stiffness matrix contributing to transverse in-plane stress components were made zero and (iii) all components of the stiffness matrix contributing to transverse out of plane stress components were made equal to zero. No interface regions between plies were modeled. It is interesting to note that for uniaxial loading the predicted strength values were precisely equal to those determined by simple ratio of the fiber direction tensile strength value and the stress concentration in the fiber direction prior to damage reported in the paper. This indicates that the progressive damage algorithm in this case did not lead to significant stress redistribution before final failure. At the time this type of analysis was pushing the computer capabilities and no mesh refinement studies were possible.

Only recently several more three-dimensional progressive damage models were developed for strength prediction in open-hole [3,4] and filled-hole laminates [5,6]. Three-dimensional property degradation modeling described in [3] was facilitated in an ABAQUS environment and consisted of modified Hashins failure criteria and associated property degradation rules. Exactly the same damage modes and property degradation rules as in [2] were used, with a significant modification being a resin rich layer, with the properties of cured matrix, between each ply was modeled in which the type (iii) stiffness degradation was applied. Due to computational constraints this layer had the same thickness as the unidirectional plies. Several examples were considered. Axial splits in a 0^0 ply emanating from a crack-type notch under axial tension were modeled. Good agreement of the experimentally observed split length as a function of load was shown. Symmetric cross-ply laminates with open holes under uniaxial tension were also considered. It was stated that the strength of the laminate was predicted with five percent accuracy, and that the presence of the resin rich layer did not significantly affect the prediction. Evaluation of damage distribution shows qualitative agreement with the radiographic image. The residual stresses were not accounted for in the analysis.

A complex boundary condition contact problem of transverse bending of a composite plate with a countersunk bolt was considered in [6]. A complete element failure approach was adopted for property degradation modeling. In this model the element stiffness was completely degraded if any one of the incorporated failure criteria was met for the average stress component values of the element. In [6] the maximum stress failure criterion was used for in-plane damage and Ye [8] delamination failure criterion for damage caused by out-of-plane stresses. Thus through the complete element failure approach, the delaminations were included in the model. No residual stresses were considered. The model was shown to produce load deflection curves in good agreement with the experimental results for the $[90_8/0_8]_s$ and $[0_8/90_8]_s$ laminates. However, no detailed correlation of the damage progression prediction was made with the experiment.

Complete degradation of the element transverse properties used in the cited works leads to unrealistic stiffness degradation results in unnotched laminates. Indeed considering a cross-ply laminate one will simultaneously find failure in all elements of the 90 ply and practically obtain ply discount result for laminate stiffness degradation, which are significantly lower than the experimental values (e.g. [9,10])

An internal state variable approach to establish property degradation rules was taken in [4,5]. Two failure mechanisms were incorporated in [4]: the matrix transverse cracking and fiber tensile breakage. The degraded stiffness matrix due to transverse cracking was represented as

$$C_{ij} = C_{ij}^0 e^{k_{ij} a_f}$$

where C_{ij}^0 was the initial (before damage) stiffness matrix, a_f the damage variable, and k_{ij} the rates of individual stiffness component degradation, established from the self-consistent model. Fiber breakage was detected from maximum strain failure criterion. Commercial finite-element package SAMSEF was chosen to implement the methodology. Numerical results presented were for the same laminates as in the two-dimensional analysis [7]. It was concluded that more realistic transverse cracking patterns in the off-axis plies were observed. The loading was modeled only up to about 85 percent of the failure, due to numerical concerns. No residual stress or delamination effects were considered.

The discrete internal state variable approach developed in [7] for two-dimensional analysis was extended in [5] for three-dimensional prediction of bearing strength in composite bolted joints. A rigid bolt was modeled and ABAQUS finite element package was used to facilitate the property degradation model. Hashin's failure criterion was used to identify the damage mode in the element. Two different sets of internal state variables, D_i^t and D_i^c , associated with tensile and compressive loads were used. Linear eight-node elements with reduced integration were used for the three-dimensional modeling with one element through the thickness of the ply. The delaminations and residual stresses were neglected. In the bearing failure mode, the analysis was stopped after the damage propagated outside the washer-covered area around the hole. The model proved capable of predicting the mode of failure: tensile, shear-out or bearing, and the initial load drop-off.

However, no attempts to verify the accuracy of the stress redistribution prediction accuracy in the vicinity of the hole due to sub critical damage, modeled by using the property degradation technique, were made in the literature to the author's knowledge.

The goals of the present paper are twofold. We shall examine the ability of the property degradation approach to model a critical damage mode, namely transverse cracking in the form of longitudinal splitting in the 0-ply and predict the fiber stress relaxation effect. Second, we shall apply a qualitatively different numerical approach [11], based on higher order shape functions, to model the effect of transverse cracking and verify its accuracy experimentally by using moiré interferometry.

PROBLEM FORMULATION

Consider a rectangular N -layer laminate built of orthotropic layers with length L in the x -direction, width A in the y -direction, and thickness H . Individual ply thicknesses are $h_p = z^{(p)} - z^{(p-1)}$, where $z = z^{(p)}$ and $z = z^{(p-1)}$ are upper and lower surfaces of the p -th ply, respectively. The origin of the x, y, z coordinate system is in the lower left corner of the plate, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of the composite plate with an open hole test specimen.

A circular opening of diameter D with the center at $x=x_c$ and $y=y_c$ is considered. Uniaxial loading is applied via displacement boundary conditions at the lateral sides ($x=0, L$), while all other boundaries were kept free:

$$\begin{aligned}
-u_x(0, y, z) &= u_x(L, y, z) = u_L / 2, \\
u_y(0, y, z) &= u_y(L, y, z) = 0,
\end{aligned}
\tag{1}$$

The transverse displacement is not constrained aside from a rigid body constant. The constitutive relations in each ply are as follows:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}^p (\varepsilon_{kl} - \alpha_{kl}^p \Delta T)
\tag{2}$$

where C_{ijkl}^p and α_{kl}^p are elastic moduli and thermal expansion coefficients of the p-th orthotropic ply, and ΔT is the temperature change.

STRESS REDISTRIBUTION EXAMINATION DUE TO TRANSVERSE CRACKS MODELED BY USING PROPERTY DEGRADATION METHOD

We shall examine the ability of the property degradation approach to model a critical damage mode, namely transverse cracking in the form of longitudinal splitting in the 0-ply and predict the fiber stress relaxation effect. To isolate this effect we shall consider the strength prediction in the [0₈] laminate next.

The experimentally observed failure mode of this laminate is development of transverse cracks or splits emanating from the hole which reduce the stress concentration in the fiber direction, and provide the strength of the laminate equal to that of the ligament strength. This mechanism will be present in the laminate, where the splits may not propagate through the entire length of the laminate and will only provide partial stress concentration relief. Typical finite-element subdivision, shown in Figure 2, will be used.

The property degradation based progressive damage modeling in this one ply composite will be performed by using degradation rules (i) and (ii), corresponding to full degradation of the element stiffness matrix and all components contributing to the transverse components of stress, depending whether fiber tensile failure or transverse cracking failure criterion were satisfied. Maximum stress failure criterion examined in the center of the elements was used. The stiffness and strength properties of IM7/5250-4 unidirectional composite [9,10] were used, where $E_{11}=22.15\text{Msi}$, $E_{22}=1.300\text{Msi}$, $E_{33}=1.300\text{Msi}$, $\nu_{13}=\nu_{12}=0.327$, $\nu_{23}=0.477$, $G_{13}=0.867\text{Msi}$, $G_{23}=0.477\text{Msi}$, $G_{12}=0.867\text{Msi}$, $\alpha_{11}=2.500\text{E-}07/^{\circ}\text{F}$, $\alpha_{22}=1.400\text{E-}05/^{\circ}\text{F}$. The strength properties, such as fiber tensile and compressive strength, transverse tensile and compressive strength, and in-plane shear strength were $X_t=349.7\text{Ksi}$, $X_c=303\text{Ksi}$, $Y_t=9.610\text{Ksi}$, $Y_c=41.39\text{Ksi}$, and $S_{12}=14.51\text{Ksi}$

The progressive failure analysis, however, predicts early onset of fiber breakage due to inability to model the stress relief in the fiber direction. To illustrate this fact the following numerical example was considered. In the finite-element mesh shown in Figures 2a and 2b, all the elements with the center coordinates x_i, y_i, z_i , such that $y_c - D/2 < y_i < y_c + D/2$, were assigned to have in-plane matrix cracking-type damage (ii). This band of elements is darkened in Figure 2. The mesh size is chosen sufficiently small, so that the roughness of the edges of this band near the hole is much smaller than the hole diameter. The radial distribution of the hoop stress $\sigma_{\theta\theta} / \sigma_0$ normalized to applied far-field stress is shown in Figure 3. The two mesh densities yield practically equal hoop distribution for virgin laminates. In the presence of massive transverse damage, however, the hoop stress is reduced very little. Significant relief of the stress concentration can only be observed if the stiffness of the selected finite elements is completely reduced, i.e. (i)+(ii) degradation conditions applied. This assumption is physically incorrect since no massive fiber breakage in the selected regions takes place.

Figure 2. Radial Type Mesh Configurations Used for Predicting the Fiber Stress Relaxation due to Transverse Splitting: (a) Coarse Mesh; (b) Dense Mesh.

Figure 3. Normalized Hoop Stress $\sigma_{\theta\theta}/\sigma_0$ Distribution as a Function of the Distance from the Hole Edge in the Direction Perpendicular to Loading.

The demonstrated effect clearly undermines the ability of the property degradation algorithm to realistically describe stress distribution near damage sites, which in the case of laminates with holes is paramount for reliable prediction of ultimate strength. It is expected that by using more elaborate property degradation algorithms such as in [4,5,7], the degraded properties will be somewhere in between the initial stiffness and the fully degraded, and thus provide even smaller fiber stress relaxation effect.

In the following, we shall apply a qualitatively different numerical approach [11] based on higher order shape functions, to model the effect of transverse cracking and verify its accuracy experimentally by using moiré interferometry.

MESH INDEPENDENT DAMAGE MODELING BY USING HIGHER ORDER SHAPE FUNCTIONS

Consider an elastic volume V and a set of piecewise polynomial three-dimensional functions $X_i(\mathbf{x})$, which provide a partition of unity-type basis function for displacement approximation, so that

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i \in \Omega} X_i(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{U}_i, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{U}_i are displacement approximation coefficients, not necessarily associated with nodal displacements except for the boundary ∂V where boundary conditions are imposed. All values of index i in equation (3) compose set Ω . Functions $X_i(\mathbf{x})$ are constructed from one-dimensional sets of B-spline basis functions of maximum order n and nodal defect k as standard tensor products. The nodal defect of spline designates the maximum number of discontinuous derivatives in this node. If $k=1$ then $u_i(\mathbf{x}) \in C^{(n-1)}$, and in the case of $k=n-1$, one obtains C^0 continuous $p=n$ approximation. In our present work a procedure based on polynomial representation (Iarve [12]) was used. Each function $X_i(\mathbf{x})$ possesses local support of no more than $(n+1)^3$ mesh cells and

$$\sum_{i \in \Omega} X_i(\mathbf{x}) \equiv 1, \quad \mathbf{x} \in V.$$

The subdivision into mesh cells or finite elements is essential for implementation because we assume that there is an integration procedure associated with these cells, which allows us to calculate volume integrals of shape functions, and their cross products and the products of their derivatives. Our goal is to model a displacement field discontinuous along a surface Γ_α for a given mesh configuration and approximation (3).

The step function enrichment of approximation (3) proposed in Moes et al. [13] for modeling the desired discontinuity for a bisected domain V can be written as

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \tilde{H}(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{u}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}) + (1 - \tilde{H}(\mathbf{x})) \mathbf{u}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}), \quad (4)$$

$$\tilde{H}(\mathbf{x}) = H(f_\alpha(\mathbf{x}))$$

where $\mathbf{u}^{(1)}$ and $\mathbf{u}^{(2)}$ are approximated by shape functions (3), $H(x)$ is the Heaviside step function, and $f_\alpha(\mathbf{x})$ is the signed distance function for the surface Γ_α . To extend equation (4) for a crack ending inside volume V in point B , we shall define the extension of the signed distance function for a given point, in the case when the point of the crack surface nearest to it is not the orthogonal projection of that point to the crack surface. The signed distance function, is defined as

$$f_\alpha(\mathbf{x}) = \text{sign}(\mathbf{n}(\bar{\mathbf{x}})(\mathbf{x} - \bar{\mathbf{x}})) \min_{\bar{\mathbf{x}} \in \Gamma_\alpha} \|\mathbf{x} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}\|, \quad (5)$$

where Γ_α is the crack surface. In the case of the bisecting crack point, $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ is the orthogonal projection of \mathbf{x} on surface Γ_α . However, in the case when the crack ends in point B inside the region, we will find such $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ that $\bar{\mathbf{x}} = B$ according to (5), and $\mathbf{x} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}$ is not orthogonal to Γ_α . It is in this context that the signed distance function will be used below.

Let us denote the set of all index values in (3) for which the shape functions are nonzero at the crack surface by Ω_α so that

$$\exists \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_\alpha : X_i(\mathbf{x}) \neq 0 \Leftrightarrow i \in \Omega_\alpha.$$

The enriched approximation for the domain V and arbitrary crack is defined in the following form

$$\mathbf{u} = \tilde{H}\mathbf{u}^{(1)} + (1 - \tilde{H})\mathbf{u}^{(2)} + \mathbf{u}^{(3)}, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{u}^{(1)} = \sum_{i \in \Omega_\alpha} X_i \mathbf{U}_i^{(1)}, \quad \mathbf{u}^{(2)} = \sum_{i \in \Omega_\alpha} X_i \mathbf{U}_i^{(2)}, \quad (7)$$

and

$$\mathbf{u}^{(3)} = \sum_{i \in \Omega/\Omega_\alpha} X_i \mathbf{U}_i^{(3)}. \quad (8)$$

We have also omitted the spatial argument for conciseness. Strictly speaking, the strains are assumed independently, as

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \tilde{H}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(1)} + (1 - \tilde{H})\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(2)} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(3)}, \quad (9)$$

where the strain tensors $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(1)}$, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(2)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(3)}$ are expressed through $\mathbf{u}^{(1)}$, $\mathbf{u}^{(2)}$ and $\mathbf{u}^{(3)}$ by using linear strain-displacement relationship, and the step function is not differentiated. Considering the elastic stress-strain relationship:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon},$$

one can write the strain energy in the volume V as

$$W = \int_V \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \tilde{H} [\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(1)}]^T \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(1)} + \frac{1}{2} (1 - \tilde{H}) [\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(2)}]^T \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(2)} + \frac{1}{2} [\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(3)}]^T \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(3)} + \tilde{H} [\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(1)}]^T \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(3)} + (1 - \tilde{H}) [\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(2)}]^T \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(3)} \right\} dV \quad (10)$$

The work of external traction \mathbf{T} applied at the portion S_T of the boundary ∂V is expressed as

$$A = \int_{S_T} \mathbf{T} \mathbf{u} dS, \quad (11)$$

where the displacement is approximated by using equation (6). The minimum potential energy principle, used to obtain the equations for determining unknown displacement approximation coefficients, can be expressed as:

$$\delta(W - A) = 0. \quad (12)$$

The idea of the method proposed in this paper is to replace the step function in equations (6)-(12) by an approximation based on shape functions (3), so that

$$\tilde{H}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i \in \Omega} X_i(\mathbf{x}) h_i. \quad (13)$$

In this case all integrals appearing in the system of equations resulting from (12) will contain products of unaltered original shape functions and their derivatives. The orders of polynomials to be integrated in the mesh cells are higher but always the same, thus a standard Gaussian quadrature can be employed. Equations (6)-(12) completely determine the displacement approximation coefficients in equations (7) and (8) provided that the coefficients h_i are defined. It is worth noting that extending the crack, i.e. changing the set Ω_{α} the total number of degrees of freedom in equation (6) also changes, since duplicate degrees of freedom are required for each function with the index belonging to Ω_{α} .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A $[0/+45/90/-45]_s$ IM7/5250-4 composite with a 6.35 mm diameter hole loaded in uniaxial tension was analytically examined using the mesh independent damage modeling technique proposed above and experimentally examined using moiré interferometry [14]. The test specimen, with dimensions 300 mm x 38 mm x 1.6 mm, was initially loaded to 14,500 N in a hydraulic testing machine to induce damage (see Figure 1). It was then examined in a moiré interferometer under 2670 N tensile loading applied with a hand-operated screw driven load frame. Displacement fringe patterns were digitally recorded and analyzed using a phase-shifting method of the type described in Lassahn, et al. [15]. X-ray inspection was used to quantify the extent of matrix cracking in the specimen. The 0° splits were modeled using the analytical procedure described above. All other damage (cracks in the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° plies) was ignored in the analysis.

A digitally generated y-direction displacement fringe pattern, resulting from the moiré interferometry testing, is shown in Figure 4 with contour intervals of 200 nm/fringe. The outline of the crack is visible near the bottom of the hole.

Figure 4: Moiré interferometry results. Y-direction displacement contours (200 nm/contour).

The experimental fringe image is shown again in Figure 5 superimposed onto analytically generated contour maps. The analytical contour maps are from separate load steps. The first step (Figure 5.a) contains no damage while the second load step (Figure 5.b) contains 0° cracks of a length that best matched the experimental situation. It is clear that the displacement match improves with the addition of cracking in the analytical model.

Figure 5: Comparison of analytical and experimental y-direction displacement contours (200 nm/contour). (a) Analytical results without cracking and (b) with cracking.

The analytical and experimental axial strain distribution near the hole is shown in Figure 6. Again, the addition of the crack in the analytical model clearly improves the prediction of axial strain in the 0° ply. These results show the reduction in axial strain concentration at the hole edge resulting from matrix cracking in the 0° ply. This strain component is critical in the prediction of ultimate strength of the laminate.

Figure 6: Analytical (damaged and undamaged) and experimental axial strain along the line $x=0$.

CONCLUSIONS

Three-dimensional analysis of damage progression near the open hole based on the property degradation method was performed to assess the accuracy of stress redistribution prediction due to formation of longitudinal splitting. The demonstrated effect clearly undermines the ability of the property degradation algorithm to realistically describe stress distribution near damage sites, which in the case of laminates with holes is paramount for reliable prediction of ultimate strength.

A qualitatively different approach based on application of higher order approximation to model cracking independently of the original mesh configuration employed in undamaged composites was utilized to model splitting near the open hole in the zero degree plies in a quasi-isotropic composite.

Moiré interferometry was performed on a quasi-isotropic laminate with zero degree surface plies containing an open hole. In preloaded specimens containing longitudinal splits in the surface layers, full field displacement measurements were performed in the vicinity of the hole. The fiber direction stress relaxation at the hole edge predicted by the mesh independent crack modeling method agreed well with the experimental data.

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